

Numerical simulation of forced convection induced in an industrial scale electrochemical reactor

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Resumen

Este trabajo presenta un análisis de dinámica de fluidos computacional de dos mecanismos de convección forzada implementados en un reactor electroquímico a escala industrial. El reactor tiene el objetivo principal de reducir el cromo hexavalente acuoso proveniente de los baños de enjuague de la industria de galvanoplastia. Los mecanismos disponibles en la planta galvanoplástica son agitación mecánica con impulsor y agitación neumática con sopladores de aire. Los resultados teóricos confirman que, debido a la geometría y la disposición de la celda electroquímica, los sopladores de aire desarrollan un flujo homogéneo, mientras que la agitación mecánica solo mejora la circulación en la zona del impulsor. Este comportamiento explica los resultados obtenidos a escala industrial, ya que la tasa de reducción de Cr(VI) es más rápida con la agitación neumática, por lo que este mecanismo debe seleccionarse.

Palabras clave: Reactor Electroquímico, Cromo Hexavalente, Simulación Numérica, Flujo de Fluidos

Abstract

This work presents a computational fluid dynamics analysis of two mechanisms of forced convection implement in an industrial scale electrochemical reactor. The reactor has the main objective of reducing aqueous hexavalent chromium from rinse baths of the electroplating industry. The mechanisms available in the manufacturing plant are mechanical agitation with an impeller and pneumatic agitation with air blowers. Theoretical results confirm that due to the geometry and arrangement of the electrochemical cell, the air blowers develop a homogeneous flow, while the mechanical agitation only enhances the circulation in the impeller zone. This behavior explains the results obtained at the industry scale since the rate of Cr(VI) reduction is faster with pneumatic agitation, so this mechanism must be selected.

Keywords: Electrochemical Reactor, Hexavalent Chromium, Numerical Simulation, Fluid Flow

Introduction

Electroplating industries are an anthropogenic source of hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) present in wastewaters. Due to the poisonous properties of Cr(VI) for mammals is necessary to remove from the waste effluents to avoid its incorporation toward the food chain [1]. Several electroplating industries in the Metropolitan Area of Mexico City are small and medium businesses that have a small gap in the amount of investment, so it is highly expensive to pay for treating their wastes [2]. The current strong environmental regulations have been to force this industry to implement technologies to make a non-polluting production.

Electrochemical reduction under acid conditions using iron electrodes has been a profitable technique in its implementation to remove Cr(VI) from the wastewaters of this industry, since that the equipment and infrastructure are very similar to the available in this kind of manufacturing plants [3]. The overall reactions of this process are:

The electrochemical reduction is based on the electro-dilution of Fe(II) from the anodes which acts as a reducing agent of Cr(VI) to trivalent chromium (Cr(III)). After the reduction, the pH of the medium is raised to nine units to cause the precipitation of the metal hydroxides [4]. The success of the electrochemical reduction depends on to maintain an acid pH and a high mass transfer during the electrolysis [5].

The present work focus on comparing two forced convection mechanism to enhance the mass transfer in an industrial scale batch electrochemical reactor. The electrochemical reactor operates in industry "Alvarez Hermanos S.A. de C.V." located industrial zone of Vallejo, Mexico City. The objective of implementing forced convection is to increase the reduction rate of Cr(VI) which implies the reduction of power consumption. The available mechanisms in the manufacturing plant are mechanical agitation with a four-blade impeller, and pneumatic agitation with air blowers connect to a stream of compressed air. The investigation of both agitation mechanism was with computational fluid dynamics (CFD) tools to resolve the flow behavior in the steady-state and evaluate the convection in all zones of the reactor. Also, plant tests were performed to confirm that improvement improvements of each mechanism in the reduction of Cr(VI) see with the CFD analysis. Experimental and numerical analyses are carried out to understand the behavior of flow especially in the zone between electrodes.

Methodology

Batch Electrochemical Reactor

The electrochemical reactor vessel has a capacity of 1250 L, with 1 m high, 0.9 m width, and 1.5 m long. The electrochemical reactor has 15 electrodes, eight were used as a cathode and seven as an anode (Fig. 1 A). The electrodes are rectangular plates of carbon steel of $\frac{1}{4}$ " thickness with 0.95 m high and 0.85 m width. The holes of electrodes are 0.85 m high and 0.05 m width (Fig. 1 B). The electrodes operation was in monopolar with a gap between electrodes of 0.03 m. A DC source was used to apply a current of 100 A through the electrode holders.

A

B

Figure 1. Pictures of the industrial-scale electrochemical reactor.

Mechanical and pneumatic agitation was applied for separate mechanisms of forced convection for the electrolytic solution. Mechanical agitation was achieved with a four flat blade turbine to improve the radial circulation between electrodes. The diameter of the impeller (D) is 0.3 m, and the paddle has 0.02 m thickness and 0.05 m high. The impeller shaft was placed 20 cm from the wall of the vessel and left a bottom clearance of 0.475 m. The shaft of the impeller was fixed in a motor to achieve a velocity of 1000 rpm. Pneumatic agitation was implemented with three air blowers equal spaced in the midplane of the bottom vessel to improve the axial circulation in the electrochemical cell (Fig. 2).

Each air blower has a quadratic area of 0.01 m², which generated bubbles with a mean diameter of 0.0015 m. The air blowers were connected to the stream of compressed air to produce a flow of 60 L min⁻¹.

Numerical simulation strategy

A commercial code Ansys Fluent® was used to resolve the partial differential equations of moment and mass with the numerical method of finite volume. The full domain of the reactor was considered to resolve the spatial development of the flow field. The pre-processing software Ansys Meshing® was used to discretize the domain in tetrahedral control volumes. Patch conforming method was used to build the grid in the whole domain and local size method functions were implemented to refine in walls of interest (i.e. electrodes, air inlets, and impeller). Then, in Ansys Fluent® the elements were converted to polyhedral, to improve the quality (Maximum Skewness and Minimum Orthogonal Quality was 0.79 and 0.2, respectively) and reduce the size of the grid. Grid independence study was carried out using the solution of the mechanical agitation and result in an optimum size of ~2.3 million elements (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Computational domain of electrochemical reactor. Only one electrode is shown so as not to obstruct the view of the polyhedral elements near the wall.

Two mechanisms of forced convection apply in the reactor needs specially treat to establish a CFD simulation. In both cases the convection caused by the cathodic hydrogen is neglect, therefore, the properties of the electrolytic solution were supposed to equal the water at standard conditions. The operating conditions of the electrochemical cell allow us to suppose isothermal and incompressible flow for the CFD analysis. The next two sections explain the considerations for simulating the impeller motion and the air dispersion in the reactor.

Simulation of mechanical agitation

Multiple reference frame (MRF) method is an approach widely implement to simulate the rotation of the impeller, since saving of the calculation time with a good approximation of the mean flow [6]. The MRF method needs to divide the domain into regions named rotating reference frame (RRF) and stationary reference frame (SRF). The Navier-Stokes equations are formulated for each reference frame as follow:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \vec{v}) + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{v} \otimes \vec{v}) = -\nabla P + \nabla \cdot \tau - \rho[\vec{\omega} \times (\vec{\omega} \times \vec{r}) + 2\vec{\omega} \times \vec{v}] \quad (2)$$

where \vec{v} is the instantaneous vector of the velocity of the reference frame, τ is the tensor of viscous stresses, $\vec{\omega}$ is the angular velocity of the reference frame. The origin of the coordinates system is in the center of impeller, thus \vec{r} denoted the vector position respect to the origin. The last two terms of equation 2 are the centrifuge and the Coriolis force, respectively. In this work, the RRF is a volume of the revolution that involves the impeller and the SRF is the rest of the vessel (Fig. 2). The top

surface of liquid was assumed as an "inviscid wall" using symmetry boundary condition, while in the rest of the walls "no-slip condition" was applied with standard wall functions. The impeller wall is the only moving wall, therefore its velocity is set relative to the adjacent cell zone (RRF). The discretization for all flow field variables was achieved with second-order upwind schemes, and the system of algebraic equations is solved using the SIMPLE algorithm. The steady-state solution was stopped when residuals of velocities reach values $< 10^{-4}$.

Simulation of pneumatic agitation

Pneumatic agitation was applied through with the bubble's dispersion; therefore, the flow needs multiphase modeling. The disperse phase of air in a continua medium of liquid water has been successfully predicted with Euler-Euler model, where the momentum equation for each phase, p , are formulated as follow:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\alpha_p \rho_p \vec{v}_p) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_p \rho_p \vec{v}_p \otimes \vec{v}_p) = -\alpha_p \nabla P + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_p \tau_p) + \alpha_p \rho_p g + R_p \quad (3)$$

where ρ_p , \vec{v}_p , τ_p are the density, velocity, and viscous stress of each phase, p , α_p denote the phase volume fraction ($\alpha_L + \alpha_G = 1$), and R_p represents the terms of interphase momentum exchanges. In the airlift reactors, the main interphase momentum exchange is related to drag force between air bubbles and liquid media, hence the mass and lift force is neglect in this work [7]. For the drag force calculation, the drag coefficient is estimated by the correlation of Schiller and Naumann [8]. The surface tension of the interphase water-air is assumed constant ($0.073 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$). Three types of boundary conditions are implanted in this case: (1) velocity inlet in the air blower surface to set the normal velocity magnitude of air ($0.1 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$), (2) "no-slip condition" with standard wall functions at all vessel, electrode and impeller walls (3) symmetry in the upper part of the domain to only allow the escape of air through that surface. The pseudo transient formulation was performed to solve the steady-state. At the beginning of simulations, all domain was patch as water. First-order upwind schemes were applied to all flow field variables to avoid the instabilities of convergence reports in this kind of flows [9]. The SIMPLE coupled algorithm was applied, and convergence was assumed when residuals values of momentum were below 10^{-4} .

Turbulence modeling

Due to the inherent turbulent flow in the two mechanisms of agitation, the average time modeling of the turbulence is using with the standard κ - ϵ model. This approach has been used to modeling the flow of agitated tanks [10] and airlift reactors [9] with good agreement with experimental validation. In the case of the Euler-Euler model, the continua phase is liquid water, and the diluted phase is air, therefore the dispersed standard κ - ϵ model is implemented to calculate the turbulent proprieties in the water flow. The standard values of the empirical constants of the model are used in this work ($C_{1\epsilon} = 1.44$, $C_{2\epsilon} = 1.92$, $C_\mu = 0.09$, $\sigma_\kappa = 1.0$ and $\sigma_\epsilon = 1.3$).

Experiments in plant

Two mechanisms implemented in real operation to evaluate its efficiency to carry out the reduction of Cr(VI). Before of fill the reactor, the electrodes were sanded to encourage all tests to be performed under the same conditions. The wastewater was fed to the batch electrochemical reactor from the rinse baths of the plant. A DC source was used to apply a current of 100 A. Due to electrolysis of water ions OH^- are formed in the cathode, so that to control the pH H_2SO_4 was used. During the operation samples of 10 mL were taken from the reactor at different times. The sample's pH was raised with four drops of NaOH 8M and filtering to remove all hydroxides (FeOH_3 and CrOH_3). The diphenylcarbazide method [11] was used in the filtered solution to determine the residual Cr(VI). The data of the residual concentration of Cr(VI) was adjusted to a variable order kinetic model [12].

Results

Flow patterns

Each mechanism of agitation develops a specific behavior of the electrolytic solution inside of the reactor. The four flat blade turbine generates a typical radial pattern for this kind of agitators (Fig. 3 A) because the suction of fluid is from the top and bottom of the impeller and expulses by the radial section. Due to the presence of the vessel wall and electrode near the discharge region of the impeller, the axial component of the suction areas increases considerably. When the fluid transport through electrodes, the velocity speeds are only high between the first four electrodes, generating two strong recirculation regions in the upper and bottom part of the impeller. This fact is explained by the impact of the fluid with the electrode walls, that cause dissipation of energy from the fluid motion.

Figure 3. Contour plot of axial velocity in the midplane zy. Agitation (A) Mechanical and (B) Pneumatic.

In the case of the pneumatic agitation, the flow is predominantly axial due to the presence of air blowers that drag to the water to circulate in a positive axial form near of the inlets of air and recirculate in the negative axial form to reincorporated to the positive streamlines (Fig. 3 B). Three zones of axial recirculation are formed, one in each air blower. The air blower located out of electrodes causes the smaller velocities because the air is more dispersed than in the other two inlets, in which the electrodes keep the gas in a smaller volume and causes a rapid rise of air (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Contour plot of air volume fraction in the midplane zy.

Macro mixing parameters

Macro mixing parameters have been applied to characterize the flow development in the multistage stirred vessel [13]. Flow field results permits calculate the axial flow ($Q_{ax}(z)$) on a given cross-sectional plane (A) with the next expression:

$$Q_{ax}(z) = \int_A |v_z^+| dA \quad (4)$$

where v_z^+ are the upward component of axial velocity and dA is the differential area defined by the product of $dx dy$. The $Q_{ax}(z)$ can be obtained at different heights of the vessel for each case. Analyzing the profiles of $Q_{ax}(z)$ in both cases, the mechanical agitation achieve five times bigger axial flows than pneumatic agitation (Fig. 5). The increment of $Q_{ax}(z)$ can be explained by the impeller suction in the region out of electrodes described in the previous section (Fig. 3 A). On the other hand, the profile of $Q_{ax}(z)$ in the pneumatic agitation is more homogeneous along with the height of the reactor as a result of the flow generated by the three air blowers (Fig. 5 and Fig. 3-B).

Figure 5. Profiles of axial flow in both mechanisms of agitation. The black line and the dotted line represent Q_{Aax} for the mechanical and pneumatic agitation respectively

Using the local values of the $Q_{ax}(z)$ is possible to determine the average axial flow (Q_{Aax}) in the whole vessel. This parameter is useful because it permits calculate with the steady-state solution the axial circulation time as follows:

$$t_{ax} = \frac{V_L}{Q_{Aax}} \quad (5)$$

For each mechanism, the axial circulation is 4.21 and 20.69 s for mechanical and pneumatic agitation, respectively. It concluded that the macromixing parameters using in this work are five times better for the mechanical than the pneumatic agitation.

Velocity profiles between electrodes

To determine the better mechanism that enhances the convection of the electrolytic solution between electrodes, three lines are defined at different heights ($z = 0.05, 0.55, 0.95$ m) to extract the local axial velocities (Fig. 6). The velocity profile of line 1 is more pronounced with mechanical agitation, especially in the region near impeller discharge ($-0.35 > y > -0.15$). However, in lines 2 and 3, the

local velocities are bigger in the case of pneumatic agitation, due to the loss of dynamic pressure of the flow in the first electrodes near the impeller region. This fact promotes that the spatial distribution of the local axial velocities been more homogeneous along the electrodes in pneumatic agitation rather than mechanical agitation.

Figure 6. Profiles of the local axial velocities at different heights. The location of the lines is shown by numbers 1, 2, and 3.

Cr(VI) reduction

The data of residual concentration of Cr(VI) was adjusted to equation 4 (fig. 7), resulting in the kinetic constants of $k_1 = 0.053 \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $k_2 = 0.11 \text{ L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$ for mechanical agitation, while for pneumatic agitation the constants are $k_1 = 0.045 \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $k_2 = 0.009 \text{ L}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$. As can be seen in Fig. 7, the mechanical agitation is less efficient to promote the Cr(VI) reduction due to the poor diffusion of the Fe(II) released from the anode to the bulk solution. The pneumatic agitation promotes high velocities in the surface of the electrodes (Fig. 6), hence, promotes the best diffusion in overall volume with a homogeneous circulation.

Figure 7. Reduction of Cr(VI) at the plant. Dots represent the experimental data and lines the kinetic model prediction. The capital letter M and P in label means Mechanical and Pneumatic agitation.

Conclusions

The batch electrochemical reactor used in this industry to reduce the Cr(VI) can improve the performance with the induced forced convection. From the two options to induces forced convection available in the manufacturing plant, CFD modeling and experiments demonstrate that pneumatic agitation is the best choice, due to homogeneous flow in the overall tank promotes a high rate of

reduction. To improve this efficiency of reduction, the industry needs to invest in a novel electrochemical cell configuration that can be designed by CFD tools.

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